

9th Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society Symposium (IBICS-9)

Report by: Diego Montagner

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Venue: JHL4, John Hume Building,
Maynooth University

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Organising Committee: Dr. Diego Montagner* (Chair), Prof. Kevin Kavanagh (Co-Chair), Giulia Ferrari, Daryl Reidy, Esther Akingbagbohun

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Organisation: Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS).

Event Sponsors

Maynooth University, Anton Paar, Clinisciences, Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences, GPE, Scientific Laboratory Supplies (SLS), Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland.

CliniSciences Group

Summary

The 9th Symposium of the Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS-9) was held at Maynooth University on Friday, 31st October 2025. The annual IBICS symposia showcase recent work from researchers who work at the interface of inorganic chemistry and the life sciences, and provides an opportunity for networking between society members and industry representatives (www.ibics.ie). At IBICS-9, over 80 attendees were present, including academics at all levels, from early career researchers to principal investigators, and industry sponsors and exhibitors. Two plenary speakers headed the scientific programme;

Prof. Sylvestre Bonnet (University of Leiden, NL) and Prof. Kevin Kavanagh (Maynooth University). Three invited lectures were presented by Dr. Darren Griffith (RCSI), Prof. Angela Scala (University of Messina, IT) and Dr. Francesca Novara, (Wiley-VCH). Aligned with the spirit of IBICS, the remaining contributions to the symposium came from early career researchers with several excellent presentations, three flash presentations, and 21 poster presentations. The event was a huge success, thanks to the strong engagement from our Irish biological inorganic community and the fantastic financial support from industry sponsors. The short programme is shown below.

Attendees

Postgraduate and postdoctoral researchers, academics, and industry exhibitors/representatives made up most of the 80+ attendees at IBICS-9, working diversely across fields of inorganic chemistry and its interface with the life sciences. There was an excellent balance of female and male representation, from across different Irish institutions and beyond, and this was reflected in our symposium programme (Table 1).

Target audience: academics, postgraduate researchers, postdoctoral researchers, early career (academia).

Table 1. IBICS-9 Programma

Time	Speaker and title of presentation	Code
10:00	Registration and poster setup	
10:30	Opening remarks – Dr. Luca Ronconi, IBICS President	
Session 1 - Chair: Prof. Michael Devereux		
10:40	Plenary: Prof. Sylvestre Bonnet (University of Leiden), sponsored by Anton-Paar <i>Ruthenium-based photoactivated chemotherapy for the treatment of cancer: recent developments</i>	PL1
11:20	Dr. Darragh McHugh (University of Galway)	O1
11:35	Giulia Ferrari (Maynooth University)	O2
11:50	Invited: Prof. Darren Griffith (Royal College of Surgeon in Ireland), sponsored by CliniSciences Group <i>Exploiting Click and IEDDA Chemistry in the Development of Pt(II) Anticancer Probes</i>	IL1
12:20	Flash Presentation Session – Chair Dr. Orla Howe Amani Al Riyami, Tara McInerney, Wanyujin Wang	F1- F3
12:35	Lunch (provided)	
12:35	Poster Session Sponsored by RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section and ICI Institute of Chemistry of Ireland	P
13:40	IBICS Annual General Meeting	
Session 2 - Chair: Prof. Tia Keys		
14:00	Invited: Dr. Francesca Novara (Wiley-VCH) <i>Opening the Editor's Black Box: Insider Tips for Successful Submissions</i>	IL2
14:30	Daniel Graczyk (University College of Dublin)	O3
14:40	Nidhi Singh (University of Galway)	O4
14:55	Invited: Prof. Angela Scala (University of Messina), sponsored by GPE <i>Metals in hybrid drug delivery nanosystems: role, applications and perspectives</i>	IL3
15:25	Coffee Break	F4- F6
Session 3 - Chair: Prof. Deirdre Fitzgerald Hughes		
15:45	Federica Brescia (University of Galway)	O5
16:00	Dr. Judith Fodor (Trinity College Dublin)	O6
16:15	Plenary: Prof. Kevin Kavanagh (Maynooth University), sponsored by Anton-Paar <i>A tale of two metals; Uncovering the mode of action of novel Silver and Gallium complexes</i>	PL2
Session 4 – Chair: Dr. Luca Ronconi		
16:55	IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award Sponsored by Frontiers in Molecular Bioscience Dr. Darren Fergal Beirne (Dublin City University) <i>Pt(IV) – Sunitinib dual action pro-drugs display enhanced activity against Renal cancer types</i>	GM
17:15	Prize-giving and closing remarks – Dr. Luca Ronconi	
17:30	Wine reception	

Programme

IBICS-9 was a full one-day event, running from welcome and registration at 10am to closing remarks and reception at 5.30pm. Across four sessions, the scientific programme comprised twelve oral presentations contributed by two plenary speakers, three invited Ireland-based speakers, the IBICS Gold Medal Award winner, and six early career researchers. In addition, three flash presentations showcased a sample of the twenty-one poster presentations that were displayed at the designated poster sessions sponsored by the RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section and ICI. Each session was chaired by a leading academic in the field of bioinorganic chemistry. The IBICS AGM was held during the lunch break of the symposium.

Proceedings

The IBICS president, **Dr. Luca Ronconi** (University of Galway), officially opened the symposium giving an overview of the history of IBICS symposia and the scientific programme to follow.

Session 1 – Chair: Prof. Michael Devereux (TUD)

Our first international *plenary speaker*, **Prof. Sylvestre Bonnet** from the University of Leiden (NL) kicked off scientific presentations with a lecture focused on “Ruthenium-based photoactivated chemotherapy for the treatment of cancer: recent developments”. This lecture was sponsored by **Anton-Paar**.

Next, **Dr. Darragh McHugh** (University of Galway) presented on “A pH-responsive Zinc Metal-Organic Framework for Triple Negative Breast Cancer Chemotherapy: Insights from a 3D Tumour Model”.

Giulia Ferrari (Maynooth University) gave a talk on “Deferoxamine-Pt(IV) conjugates for theranostic applications in osteosarcoma”.

Dr. Darren Griffith (RCSI) was the first invited speaker who show some recent works in his research group with a talk on “Exploiting Click and IEDDA Chemistry in the Development of Pt(II) Anticancer Probes”.

Prof. Orla Howe (TUD) chaired the Flash presentation section with three presenters, Amani Al Riyami (TCD), Tara McInerney (UCC), Wanyujin Wang (UCD).

Following lunch and the poster session, the **IBICS AGM** was held with good attendance from members at the

symposium. New officers were elected for the coming year, with Prof. Orla Howe taking on the position of President, Prof. Deirdre Fitzgerald-Hughes elected Vice-President, and Dr. Joseph Byrne elected Secretary.

Session 2 – Chair: Prof. Tia Keys (DCU)

Restarting proceedings after the AGM was our second *invited speaker*, **Dr. Francesca Novara**, Editor in Chief of Wiley-VCH who delivered a presentation on “Opening the Editor’s Black Box: Insider Tips for Successful Submissions”.

Next, **Daniel Graczyk** (UCD) presented recent work on “Photophysical Study of the DNA Binding of Cr(III) and Os(II)

Polypyridyl Complexes with Extended Intercalating Ligands”

Picture of the attendees of the IBICS-9 Symposium (top) and picture of the IBICS Committee (bottom)

Nidhi Singh (University of Galway) discuss some recent advances on “Novel Platinum-Based Mitocans for the Treatment of Resistant Cancers: Synthesis, Targeted Delivery and Biological Studies”.

The third invited lecturer (sponsored by **GPE Scientific**) was delivered by **Prof. Angela Scala** (University of Messina, IT) with a lecture whose topic was Metals in hybrid drug delivery nanosystems: role, applications and perspectives

Session 3 – Chair: Prof. Deirdre Fitzgerald Hughes (RCSI)

Session commenced with a presentation from **Frederica Brescia** (University of Galway) who presented on a new approach to the “Design, Development and Biological Evaluation of Gold(III)-Glycoconjugates as Antiviral Agents against Coronaviruses”.

The next contribution came from **Dr. Judith Fodor** (TCD) who discussed “Investigation of Transition Metal Complexes with Multimodal Biological Activity for Photodynamic Therapy”.

The second plenary lecture (sponsored by **Anton Paar**) was delivered by **Prof. Kevin Kavanagh** (Maynooth University) with a lecture entitled “A tale of two metals; uncovering the mode of action of novel Silver and Gallium complexes”.

Session 4 – Chair: Dr. Luca Ronconi

The last Session, chaired by outgoing IBICS President Dr. Ronconi, comprised the presentation of **Dr. Darren Beirne** (Maynooth University), who is this years’ winner of the **IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award**, sponsored by **Frontiers in**

Molecular Biosciences. Darren’s award lecture centred on his recent PhD work “Pt(IV)–Sunitinib dual action pro-drugs display enhanced activity against” under the supervision of Dr. Diego Montagner.

The symposium was closed out by IBICS president, **Dr. Luca Ronconi**, with the presentation of prizes, his farewell address, and an invitation for all to join the wine reception for further discussion on the excellent presentations delivered throughout the symposium.

Presentation of gifts to plenary speakers, Prof. Bonnet (left) and Prof. Kavanagh (right).

Presentation of gifts to invited speakers, Dr. Novara (top), Dr. Griffith (left), and Dr. Scala (right).

Prizes

The **IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal**, sponsored by **Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences** was this year awarded to **Dr. Darren Beirne** from Maynooth University (Montagner’s group). The Gold Medal is awarded

annually to one PhD student who has distinguished themselves across a range of criteria throughout their PhD with a focus on research performance, achievements and impact in the field of medicinal and biological inorganic chemistry across the island of Ireland. The IBICS award selection committee also recognised the high standard of applications with high commendations given to Federica Brescia and Dr. Darragh McHugh from University of Galway.

Dr. Luca Ronconi (IBICS President), presenting Dr. Darren Beirne with the 2025 IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award, sponsored by Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences.

Dr. Luca Ronconi (IBICS President), with the highly commended Federica Brescia (left) and Dr. Darragh McHugh (right) with their postgraduate award.

The IBICS president presented three sponsored prizes during the closing remarks of the symposium. Awardees in each category were selected by our independent panel of judges.

Firstly, the **ICI Best Oral Presentation** was awarded to **Daniel Graczyk (UCD)** and the **RSC two poster presentation prizes** were awarded to **Stefania Scurtu (DCU)** and **Esther Akingbagbohun (Maynooth University)**.

ICI Best Oral Presentation Prize was awarded to Daniel Graczyk (UCD).

RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section Best Poster Prize was awarded to Stefania Scurtu (left) and Esther Akingbagbohun (right).

The Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS)

The Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS) – is a learned Society engaging a multi-disciplinary community of scientists seeking to advance research that crosses the interface between medicinal inorganic chemistry and biology in Ireland. The Society's mission is to develop, foster and promote a strong national network of scientists collaborating in research areas such as biology, chemistry, physics and medicine with an interest in biological inorganic chemistry.

The next symposium of the Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS-10) that will also celebrate the 10th anniversary of the IBICS, will take place at TUD during the final quarter of 2026, being led by Prof. Orla Howe and Prof. Bernie Creaven. Please see the IBICS website for event updates (<https://ibics.ie>). IBICS

welcomes any support for its symposia and the future activities of its members.

Acknowledgements

IBICS-9 was made possible by generous financial support from our sponsors: **Anton Paar** (Gold Sponsor), **Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences** (Silver Sponsor), **Clinisciences Group** and **GPE Scientific** (Bronze Sponsors), **Scientific Laboratory Supplies (SLS)**, **Maynooth University** via the Impact Dissemination Support Fund, **Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section** and **Institute of Chemistry of Ireland**. Many of our sponsors exhibited at the event and contributed to a vibrant meeting.

The local organising committee is grateful to the IBICS Steering Committee for additional support, particularly Luca Ronconi, Deirdre Fitzgerald-Hughes, Orla Howe and Celine Marmion. The local committee also thanks our colleagues at Maynooth University for facilitating our hosting of IBICS-9.

A particular thank you to Giulia Ferrari for the preparation of the programme, to Daryl Reidy for the photographs and to Esther Akingbagbohun for all the logistics.

IBICS-9 local organising committee, from left: Kevin Kavanagh, Esther Akingbagbohun, Daryl Reidy, Giulia Ferrari and Diego Montagner

Previous Events in this Series

8th Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society Symposium (IBICS-8), University College Cork: C. S. Burke*, T. McInerney, R. Galway, J. Stack and W. Daly, *Irish Chemical Events*, 2024, **1**, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14872697](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14872697)

7th Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society Symposium (IBICS-7), University College Dublin: J. P. Byrne* and S. Kavanagh, *Irish Chemical Events*, 2023, **1**, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14052293](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14052293)

Programmes and event reports for all previous IBICS symposia are available at: <https://ibics.ie/ibics-symposia>